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FAITH IN FOLK HEALERS: EXAMINING PATIENTS' BELIEFS IN QUACK DOCTORS IN THE RURAL COMMUNITY OF ABUYOG, LEYTE

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological qualitative study explores the beliefs and trust of Filipino patients in folk healing as an alternative to medical professionals. Five participants were purposively selected. Data collection involved semi-structured interviews and observations to investigate cultural, emotional, and experiential factors influencing patient preference. Thematic analysis of the narratives yielded five major themes: (1) Patients' Beliefs and Perceptions of Folk Healing, (2) Influence of Family and Community Support, (3) Mistrust of Modern Healthcare, (4) Financial and Geographic Accessibility, and (5) Rituals and Healing Practices. The study highlights a research gap in explicitly understanding the specific cultural, emotional, and experiential reasons why some Filipino patients trust folk or quack healers over conventional medical practitioners. This gap calls for deeper exploration to inform culturally sensitive healthcare approaches and policy.

The study concluded that patients' preference was based on a reliance on cultural tradition, family tradition, spiritual beliefs, and emotional safety. Patients identified that their trust in folk healers well surpassed being only hunters. Folk healers gave patients familiar faces, offered spirituality, and brought emotional comfort in the times of emotional difficulty. The folk healers' mode of practice depicted local lifestyles that were still private, friendly, and accessible, and culturally safe regarding the values and beliefs of the people who sought the folk healers. Patients were able to weave together the stories of healing that containing physical disturbances, emotional wounds, and spiritual distress; aspects of life modern doctors are still blind to.

Additionally, this study highlights the rationale for relying on cultural belief systems related to health care. Learning about emotional and spiritual components of healing may lead to positive implications in significant modalities of modern health care, progress forward in holistic alternatives, and decrease reliance on traditional medicine.

Keywords: Traditional healers, hilot, tayhop, cultural beliefs, traditional medicines, rituals

Introduction

The myth about folk medicine practitioners that are popularly referred to as quack doctors remains deeply ingrained in the tradition, experience, and faith in many folks and culturally rich regions of the Philippines. But despite the advent of modern medicine, a lot of individuals resort to these healers and demand curing not only because of its availability but also because of faith, tradition, and attachment. The phenomenon poses significant questions regarding the role played by belief systems in determining health-seeking behavior and the role played by cultural heritage in determining the perception of legitimacy and care.

This study aims to address the existing gap by exploring the beliefs and experiences of patients who consult quack doctors in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. It seeks to examine how patients' socio-cultural backgrounds, previous health experiences, and perceptions of the formal healthcare system influence their decisions to seek care from folk healers rather than registered healthcare providers. By identifying these factors, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of healthcare dynamics within rural communities and provides evidence-based recommendations to improve health service delivery in the region.

Folk healing remains a significant component of healthcare in many rural in the country. A study by Posadas (2015) in Marikina City revealed that from individuals from low to middle-income backgrounds often seek folk healthcare due to trust, genuine concern from healers, and family influence. These factors persist regardless of the availability of formal healthcare services. Similarly, Palmiano and Molina (2021) reported that the student at the Central Bicol State University of Agriculture maintain a strong belief in traditional healers such as the hilot and the albularyo despite of advancements in modern medicine. Rondilla et al. (2021) observed that positive past experiences, distrust in the formal healthcare system, and family traditions are primary reasons for the continued use of folk remedies. The Department of Health (DOH) promote traditional healing as a cost-effective and accessible healthcare alternative, especially in underserved area (Philippines Information Agency, 2004). Likewise, Adovo et al. (2003) highlighted affordability, convenience, and cultural relevance.

Moreover, this study is guided by Jerome Frank's Common Factors Theory (Frank & Frank, 1993), originally developed in the field of psychotherapy. The theory posits that healing outcomes are not always determined by specific techniques, but rather by shared factors across various healing systems-such as empathy, therapeutic alliance, expectation of recovery, and cultural congruence.

Additionally, a study by Kohrt et al. (2020) in rural Nepal demonstrated that traditional healers' use rituals, empathetic engagement, and symbolic storytelling helped patients reinterpret distress and find psychological relief-similar to what is observed in Philippine rural settings. The "manghihilot" "specializes on methods and therapies that can be used for musculoskeletal disorders, fractures, and sprains. In rural areas, "hilot" can refer to both a chiropractor "(manghihilot, masahe)" and a midwife "(magpapaanak)". With a focus on diagnostic methods, the "mangluluop" typically refers patients to the albularyo, medico, or "manghihilot" for conclusive care. While the "mangtatawas" "or tawas" is a common diagnostic procedure that provides hints as to the nature and origin of the person's condition, it is thought to be a specialist who uses the ritual of "luon" to ascertain the reason for an illness (Stuart, 2003).

In addition, this paper ensures the involvement of participants with firsthand experience relevant to the study, and it is facilitated with a deep exploration of why and how people in the community still consult with quack doctor's despite of modern technologies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to investigate the faith of patients in quack doctors in Abuyog, Leyte. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions.

1. Why patients consult faith healers?
2. What are the practices of folk healers in healing their patients?
3. How do patients view the effectiveness of faith healing?
4. How do the researchers reflect on their study?
5. What intervention program can be proposed based on the result of the study?

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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative phenomenological study employed Clark Moustakas' approach to explore Filipino patients' beliefs in folk healing and understand why they prefer consulting quack doctors instead of medical physicians. Moustakas, a leading figure in phenomenological research, defines the method to uncover the universal essence of lived human experiences by interpreting participants' feelings, perceptions, and beliefs. The goal is to describe the core structure of the phenomenon, providing deep insight into the subjective experiences of individuals regarding their healing preferences.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using semi-structured interviews, which allowed participants to freely express their feelings, stories, and experiences, particularly regarding their consultations with quack doctors. This flexible interview method facilitated an in-depth exploration of participants' perspectives. Additionally, researchers conducted observations of the patients to complement and enrich the data collected from the interviews.

Validation of the Research Instrument

EXPERT REVIEW: Research instructors carefully reviewed the interview questions and approved it to confirm that it all aligns with the goal of the study. This evaluation process was aimed to ensure that all research questions were relevant and timely to the research topic and was effectively designed to gather information related to the study.

SATURATION: Data collection proceeds until data saturation was reached. Which means that additional interview was no longer needed to produce ideas, themes, or insights for the study.

TRIANGULATION: Triangulation method was employed to ensure the credibility and accuracy of the findings and were utilized multiple approaches for the verification of data. In this study several rounds of one-on-one interviews were conducted to the participants to ensure that all collected data were confirmed and validated.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. This location is selected for its diverse culture and countryside location. It has a range population of participants, diverse population, culture, and traditions, which helped in capturing real stories.

Participant Selection and Sampling

The participants were selected through purposive sampling who have relevant experience consulting with quack doctors. According to Scribbr (2023), purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling where researchers use their judgment based on characteristics or expertise to meet the study objective.

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Characteristics of the Participants

Participants Code	Sex	Age	Civil Status	How often does the consultation with a quack doctor
P1	Female	55	Married	Twice a week
P2	Female	53	Married	Once a week
P3	Female	65	Married	Once a week
P4	Female	70	Widow	Twice a week
P5	Female	78	Widow	Twice a week

Data Analysis

The obtained data from the interviews were examined with the use of thematic analysis, which allows the researchers to examine the narratives based on the participants' experiences with quack doctors in the community within qualitative data. According to Cresswell guidelines (Cresswell 2013), the researchers identified key features and grouped them into different themes made it easier to understand for the participants of the study. The themes emerged from the transcriptions and coded data were reviewed and polished to ensure accuracy and relevance to the study. Each theme was classified to highlight the belief of the participants on faith healing.

Data Collection Process

Data were gathered through a semi-structured interview with the participants. The interview process was closely monitored and based on the data saturation. This approach was ensured a detailed coverage of each participant's experience, emotion, point of views and enhance reliability, accuracy of the study. In addition, observation was conducted to capture participants behavior, interactions non-verbal cues in their natural settings. Field notes were documented the tone of conversation and cultural practice. These observations were complemented the interviewed data and providing a deeper understanding of the participants experiences.

Ethical Considerations

Consent was obtained from all participants of this study, by providing detailed information about the purpose of the study and the procedure, and participants volunteered without pressure, and they could stop answering the question anytime. Participants' identities were ensured to protect their basic information; After the study, all the gathered data were stored confidentially. Further, this study adheres to Data Privacy Act, or R.A 10173.

Research Reflexivity

To ensure transparency and maintain the relevance of the findings, a reflexive journal was utilized throughout the study. This journal documented the patients' thoughts, assumption, decisions, and actions especially on the selection of the participants, data collection. Researcher's personal experiences and values on consulting folk healers despite modern technology and medical breakthrough are also included in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are themes emerged after a thorough analyzation of data

Patients' Beliefs and Perceptions in Folk Healing

This study found that patients' beliefs in folk healing come from deep cultural traditions, community values, and personal life experiences. Their view of health blends spiritually with physical care.

This was evident in the statement of Patient 1 that says "Sa mga bata ini dinhi (luyo sa talinga) makapa nimo nga baga may bukol mahalugar ngani ton kon hain gud it iya kabutangan, maupay it bata amo tak mga apo. Dapat diri pa maglima kabulan kailangan na Mapusa, magtiniyabaw, masakitan gad. Sa akon kabahin, malooy ka. It kanan sa karobasa liwat iton sa mga kalagsan pa, an ulo sa karobasa kiskisan tima igbulad katima ig tuhog, sumpa iton sit pagngipon. Sumpa iton na sit pagngipon sit bata diri mag utod-utod magsunod-sunod o sigi la pagturok sit ngipon.

("In children, it shows up here (behind the ear), and you will notice a lump that feels like it is out of place, yet hard to pinpoint exactly. My grandchildren are generally healthy, thank goodness. But if the child is not yet five months old, it needs to be treated they were crying, discomfort, real pain. I feel pity on my side."

This finding was supported by the theory of Bandura (1986). These practices are often passed down from generation to generation, reinforcing a sense of trust and familiarity. The Filipino psyche, which encompasses its culture, folklore, religion, superstitions, saints, and mythological animals, is reflected in the ancient therapeutic procedures in addition to its evident purpose (Umali, 2015)

Influence of Family and Community

The decision to consult folk healers is often strongly influenced, suggested by someone in the family or even a friend, especially who lives in rural areas. There is no age limit for seeking out quack doctors from the young to the elderly. This creates a sense of trust and comfort from the community *Patient 1* mentioned "An naka influence saka bana ang iyang lolo ug ang iyang mga igsuon mahilig mag pa tambal sa tambalan kanang hilot-hilot, tayhop kay maupay man pud sila ana kay dako man salig sa mga tamabalan. Pati gehap na ako nadara na sa akon bana ingana naupay man pud ko." (My husband was influenced by his grandfather and siblings. They like going to the quack doctor, healing massage, and healing breath. They trust the healer a lot because it helps them. I also got used to it because of my husband, and it helped me too.)

This aligns well with the study of Bibon (2021) and Ajzen (2005) who explored the cultural transmission of folk healing practices in a rural Filipino community. The study reveals how central the family is in passing down folk healing knowledge, with skills and practices often learned through close apprenticeship and careful observation. Elders act as an important role models, guiding the younger in these traditional methods.

Mistrust in Modern Healthcare, Patients Perfective in Folk Healing

Some participants had negative experiences in health centers, fear and personal trauma linked to formal healthcare which made them turn to quack doctors instead. Just like *Patient 4* disclosed similar experience "Nasamad siya kadtong ni aging bulan imbes nga mag pa doctor ni kadto siya ug tambalan kay nahdlok siya ug doctor kay kadtong last niya na kadto doctor ge injection man siya. Mao to gi pa tayhupan niya sa tambalan aron mo hunong ag dugo na upay man pud, kay dako man pud siya ug salig sa tambalan mao pud kaluyan naupay man. (Last month, he got injured, but instead of going to the doctor, he chose to go to a local healer because he was

afraid of doctors especially after the last time, when he was given an injection. So, the healer treated the wound with some sort of herbal smoke to stop the bleeding, and it worked. He also really trusted the healer, so thankfully, the treatment was effective and helped him recover.”)

This finding is in line with the study of Levesque et al. (2013) argues that access to healthcare depends on both a patient's abilities such as knowing when care is needed, seeking help, reaching services, paying for them, and engaging in care and the health system's qualities, including approachability, acceptability, availability, affordability, and appropriateness.

Financial and Geographic Accessibility

Money and travel difficulties are often observed – it's the important reasons why people use quack doctors. Patients mentioned that hospitals costs and long trips make it hard to get modern treatment. For many, folk healing isn't just tradition – it's a practical choice when faced with limited healthcare options. Among the disclosed statements of the patients is Patient 5, who said, “Waray pasahe pag mokadto pa sa sawang, problemahon pa an kwarta pamsahi ug palit medisina. Ngan ug sa tambalan pud adi mnlá sa amon harani pwedi la baktason ug ikaw la it mag igo kun pira imo ihatag kay dire man sira mo hatag sin presyo.”

“There's no money for fare to go to the town center, and I still have to worry about money for transportation and buying medicine. But the healer is just nearby, within walking distance. You're the one who decides how much to give, because they don't set a fixed price.”

A comparable study by Sosa (2016) also found that the cost of biomedical treatments and the distance to hospitals drive patients toward traditional healers. In Marinduque, respondents cited expensive vaccines and long travel time to health facilities as primary motivations for patronizing healers like those performing Tandok or Tawak.

Faith Healing Rituals and Healing Practices (from quack doctors' narrative)

This show that the quack doctor's way of healing is shaped by personal spiritual experiences and rituals, where midnight prayers, vigils, and encounters with spirit test both courage and faith. It explains that these practices blend deep religious devotion, the use of local herbs, and meaningful rituals, showing how healing is seen not just as curing the but also as restoring balance to the spirit and community. Quack doctor best captured this experience “An akon pagtuon sa paging usa ka tambalan kumadto ako sa simbahan, sementeryo kada byernes sit gab e alas 12 midnight mangadji gamit mga linatiniya. Diri lalim nak experience sadto makuri na makaharadlok kay damo it imo ma feel na malain ngan pagmulayan ka sin mga Espiritu na daotan para makita kon muilob kaba or diri. An akon pag tambal mas best kada martes ngan byernes bisan ano na oras, pwede man gihap iba na adlaw. Nagamit ako sin mga herbal na Nakita la sa komunidad for example dahun bayabas, tuba, gabon, lana, bakos, kandila, tubig, tawas, ngan banyus.” (“My path to becoming a traditional healer began with sacred journeys to the church and cemetery every Friday at midnight. I would pray and recite holy litanies during those quiet hours, facing powerful experiences that tested my spirit. It was frightening, many strange sensations would rise, and I often felt as if dark spirits were trying to challenge me, to see if I could endure or if I would falter. This spiritual initiation thought me courage and deepened my faith. As a healer, I find Tuesday and Friday to be the most powerful days for healing, though I can perform rituals for any day, at any time. I use local herbs and materials found in the community, for example guava leaves, tuba, wild herbs, oil, healing wraps, candles, water, alum crystals, and herbal baths.”)

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This narrative supports the study of Tan (2008), as it states that several traditional healers in the Philippines go through a kind of spiritual initiation, where prayers, rituals, and sometimes they encounter with spirits, it is served as a test to know if they are truly ready to heal. Healing is not just about using herbs, oils, and natural remedies, it's about gaining strength from prayers and rituals that seek to return balance to both the body and spirit.

RESEARCH REFLEXIBILITY

A reflective statement from one of the authors of this study offering critical insight on this paper.

“At first, I did not really believe in folk healing, but my experiences changed that. In our family, we use tuba leaves as a remedy, and when I once broke my elbow, a healer massaged it with *lana* until I could move my hand again. Later, I felt the relief of hilot when I sprained my ankle, and even during coughs or fevers, my grandma's trusted healers always made me feel better. I will never forget when my painful ear swelling that medicine could not cure disappeared after a healer applied *lana*. (oil) Those moments made me realize that healing is not only about science it is also about faith, tradition, and the gentle power of touch.”

CONCLUSION

Many people in Abuyog Leyte, Philippines, still rely on quack doctors because these practices are aligned to their culture and everyday life. These traditional ways often give them comfort and are also easier to access, but it can also be risky because the healers do not have formal medical training. This shows the importance of improving health system that honors the local beliefs while also guiding the community to the safe and reliable medical care.

Moreover, this study showed that many people in the region still depend on folk healers because of (i) their strong cultural traditions, (ii) influence of family (iii) financial challenges, and even (iv) past experiences with modern healthcare.

Finally for many residents, folk healing is not just a treatment – it gives them comfort, a sense of familiarity, and trust within their community.

RECOMMENDATION

While traditional healers provide accessible and affordable care, relying solely on them poses risks due to a lack of formal medical training. Improving modern healthcare to be both higher in quality and more accessible is essential, as affordability and trust encourage utilization. Building trust between medical professionals and the community can bridge fears and doubts, connecting traditional practices with modern medicine. Addressing this issue requires a balanced approach that respects cultural beliefs while promoting safe treatments. Collaborative health programs valuing traditions and fostering mutual respect between modern and traditional healers can enhance the health and well-being of rural communities in Abuyog, Leyte while preserving their cultural identity.

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